

NEURAL NETWORK HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION FOR EMITTER IDENTIFICATION

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of a neural network hardware implementation for emitter identification. In future electronic warfare environments, pulse densities on the order of hundreds of thousands of pulses per second can be expected in any given mission. To identify hostile radar systems, a processor must be able to store enough signatures for emitters of interest that proper identifications of unknown emitters can be made. Furthermore, the processor must make this identification in "real-time". One method of performing this identification is to use neural networks. Neural networks are computing systems composed of simple processing elements called nodes; each node produces a single output from a combination of inputs from other nodes or the environment. Neural networks have been simulated performing complex pattern recognition tasks. However, these simulations were completed on serial computers, such as Sun Workstations, using high resolution, 16 to 32 bit, numbers. This paper presents the results obtained when the Electronically Trainable Neural Network (ETANN) hardware is used to perform emitter identification from time-sampled emitter waveforms. The ETANN is a low (4-6 bit) resolution, high speed (2 billion operations/sec) parallel processor implementing sigmoidal-

based backpropagation networks. This hardware was chosen due to minimal interlayer processing times, 3 μ s per layer, which can allow threat identifications to be made in a matter of microseconds. For this paper, a sigmoidal-based neural network was developed, via simulation on a DEC VAX station, to discriminate between 30 emitters. The network weights were loaded on the ETANN for performance comparisons. Due to resolution constraints, the accuracy of the ETANN was typically 10%-12% lower. However, the ETANN was able to make classifications in less than 6 μ s. This significant processing speed, with only slight degradations in performance, makes neural network architectures viable alternatives for emitter identification.

1 INTRODUCTION

The primary mission of an electronic warfare threat identification system is to detect the presence of hostile emitters and identify the emitters as quickly and accurately as possible.[1] Since pulse densities on the order of hundreds of thousands of pulses per second will be expected in any given mission, future threat identification systems must be able to make their identifications in real-time. One method of accomplishing this goal is to use a pattern recognition processing scheme based on neural network technology. This paper begins by covering some of the background

associated with pattern recognition techniques and neural network processing in general. The state of the art in neural network hardware is briefly covered, followed by a discussion of the experiments used to demonstrate the hardware. After presenting the results of the hardware classification accuracies, the paper concludes by discussing the applicability of this hardware to threat identification systems.

2 BACKGROUND

The process of classifying an unknown emitter as one of several known emitters is a standard concept of pattern recognition. That is, for most pattern recognition tasks, samples of the environment, such as samples of the emitter's waveform, are sent as a K-dimensional feature vector, $\bar{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k]$ to a pattern recognition machine which classifies \bar{x} as one of the M possible emitters. Such a pattern recognition machine makes an error whenever it identifies \bar{x} as emitter J, E_j , when \bar{x} is actually from emitter I, E_i [2]. One method of minimizing classification errors is to assign \bar{x} to E_i if $P(E_i|\bar{x}) > P(E_j|\bar{x})$. Here, $P(E_i|\bar{x})$ is the a posteriori probability of emitter I given sample \bar{x} [3]. As is usually the case, $P(E_i|\bar{x})$ isn't known directly, but can be estimated from the probability distribution of \bar{x} for each of the M possible emitters and, using Bayes' rule, calculated as

$$P(E_i|\bar{x}) = \frac{p(\bar{x}|E_i) P(E_i)}{p(\bar{x})} \quad (1)$$

Here, $p(\bar{x}|E_i)$ is the state conditional probability density function of \bar{x} and $P(E_i)$ is the a priori probability of emitter I.

The decision rule now becomes to identify the samples as being from E_i if $p(\bar{x}|E_i)P(E_i) > p(\bar{x}|E_j)P(E_j)$. Thus, by estimating the conditional densities from a set of P known data samples, we can develop pattern recognition machines, for emitter classification, which makes minimum numbers of classifications errors from a given set of known samples.

One type of pattern recognition system receiving a great deal of interest is the artificial neural network (ANN). These networks are composed of simple computing elements called nodes. Each node in the network computes a single output, based upon a single transfer function, from a weighted combination of inputs from other nodes or from the environment. With a proper combination of weights and transfer functions, ANNs have been constructed to perform many types of pattern recognition tasks. One particular ANN investigated thoroughly is the backpropagation network. Each node in this type of network computes a sigmoidal output from a linear combination of its inputs, \bar{x} , weights, \bar{w} , and biases, θ as shown in equation 2.

$$y_{out} = 1 / (1 + e^{-(\bar{w}\bar{x} + \theta)}) \quad (2)$$

These networks perform as Bayes' Optimal Discriminants [5], implementing equation 1, by partitioning the feature space into decision regions with hyperplanes. Classification is then accomplished by determining which decision region the unknown waveform is located. These networks have been extensively analyzed through simulations on main frame computers using high resolution (16-32 bit) floating point values for the inputs, weights and outputs. Only recently, in the form of Intel's Electronically Trainable Analog

Neural Network, has VLSI circuitry been commercially produced implementing this ANN.

3 ETANN HARDWARE

The ETANN is Intel's analog neural network on a single chip. Each chip contains 64 neurons and 10240 modifiable synapses. This configuration allows each neuron to have 128 weights and 12 biases. As implemented by Intel[6] the 10240 weights and biases are stored as analog transconductance values. Each weight or bias produces an analog output from an analog input voltage and a stored "synaptic" voltage. As shown in figure 1, the currents generated from these input/synapse combinations are summed, converted to a voltage and passed through a sigmoid function which outputs the following [7]

$$y_{out} = \frac{1.83}{1 + e^{-1.74(\overline{wx} + \theta)}} - .94 \quad (3)$$

This analog configuration allows each neuron in the ETANN to process the input data in parallel, bypassing the serial processing bottleneck inherent in single instruction, serial processing Von Neuman conventional computers. Through this parallel processing scheme, the ETANN is specified to operate at 3 us for each layer of neurons. Since all pattern recognition techniques can be accomplished with a two-layer network of this type [8], the ETANN could provide a classification in 6 us.[6] This increase in processing speed has been at the expense of the resolution capabilities of the inputs, outputs and weights of the network. According to Intel[6], typical resolution of the weights and inputs is 6-bits. Furthermore, the weights are limited to values of +/- 2.5 and the inputs to +/- 1. Finally, each chip is not yet

"interchangeable", there is some slight variations in the operating characteristics between chips.

4 EXPERIMENTS

The procedure to determine the classification accuracy of the ETANN was to collect "real" data, simulate a neural network on a main frame, determine the classification accuracy of this simulation, download the network weights to the ETANN and determine the classification accuracy of the ETANN.

The data patterns used to train and test the neural network are from a set of time-sampled waveforms collected from 30 known emitters. Each training and test pattern was a 16-dimensional feature vector representing measurements of the emitters waveform at intervals along the pulsed waveform. Each feature of this data was then limited to values of +/-1 through a statistical normalization technique. Figure 2 shows typical composite waveforms from three emitters.

Several neural networks were constructed using the Neural-Graphics simulator, developed by the Air Force Institute of Technology, on a NEXT computer. The neural network topology chosen was the single hidden-layer network with 16 inputs, one for each waveform measurement, in the first layer, a variable number of nodes in the middle, or hidden layer, and 30 nodes, one node representing each emitter, in the last or output layer. Since previous research indicated the number of hidden nodes needed, with no constraints, ranged from 16 to 35 [7], the simulations consisted of networks with 16, 20, 25, 30 and 35 hidden-layer nodes and 30 output layer nodes. Each node in the network computed its output based on equation 3; each weight was constrained to remain

between +/- 2.5. With one output node for each class, the classification rule was to choose the class as the highest output node.

Neural network architectures, with the same topologies of the simulations, were implemented using the ETANN hardware. The network weights, as determined by each simulation, were downloaded to the chip for analysis of the hardware. Again, the classification rule was to choose the class as the highest output node.

5 RESULTS

Table 1 shows the results, for various configurations, obtained from the neural network simulations and the networks implemented on the ETANN. From this table, it's evident the best average performance of the ETANN occurred with 35 nodes in the hidden layer. With this architecture, we then analyzed the performance of the ETANN after the networks were optimized via extensive training.

Table 2 shows the ETANN results for various simulator training times. The increase in accuracy of the ETANN from 75% to 83%, while the simulation increased only from 93% to 94%, was probably due to overcoming some of the loss in resolution of the weights from the simulation to the ETANN. Once this resolution loss had been overcome, the network performances "leveled-out" for both the simulation and the ETANN.

Finally, we evaluated the performance of five different ETANN chips configured with 35 nodes in the hidden layer and the weights obtained by 177 training iterations. These results are shown in Table 3. Though each ETANN chip was configured the same, and downloaded with the same set of weights, the accuracy of the ETANN network varied

significantly from chip to chip. This effect is probably due to both the analog architecture and developmental nature of the chips. The analog architecture of the chips, in which currents and voltages are used to perform the calculations, are, in part, a function of the characteristics of individual chips. This makes the processing less predictable, from chip to chip, than equivalent digital architectures. The chip's developmental status indicates the initial manufacturing processes aren't yet be stable enough to allow production of identical chips.

6 CONCLUSIONS

These tests show the ETANN could be a promising implementation of the ANN architecture in hardware. The processing speed of 6us for pattern recognition tasks makes the ETANN ideal for real-time applications such as emitter identification. However, two drawbacks need to be overcome before the ETANN architecture could be implemented in military systems. First, the ETANN's classification accuracy is not yet able to match accuracies obtained through simulations. This is probably due to the loss in resolution of the inputs and weights associated with the ETANN chip and the chips analog nature in general. A method needs to be found to increase the classification accuracies without resorting to "on-chip" training. Finally, the ETANN chips are not yet interchangeable. This lack of consistency from chip to chip is probably due to the fact that "first-generation" chips were used in this experiment. Once these two problems are overcome, the ETANN could prove a viable method of identifying emitters in real-time.

7 REFERENCES

1. Filippo Neri, *Introduction to Electronic Defense Systems*. Norwood, MA: Artech House, Inc. 1991
2. Duda and Hart, *Pattern Classification and Scene Analysis*. New York: Wiley and Sons Inc, 1973.
3. J. T. Tou And R. C. Gonzalez, *Pattern Recognition Principles*, Reading MA: Addison-Wesley Publishing Co. 1974.
4. Wasserman, Philip D. *Neural Computing, Theory and Practice*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold, 1989.
5. Ruch, D and others. "The Multilayer Perceptron as an Approximation to a Bayes' Optimal Discriminant Function." *International Joint Conference on Neural Networks*, pages 863-873.
6. Intel Corporation. 80170NX *Electronically Trainable Analog Neural Network*. Product Manual, Order Number: 290408-002, Intel Corporation, Santa Clara CA (June 91).
7. Calvin, James B. *ETANN Hardware Implementation for Radar Emitter Identification*, Masters Thesis, School of Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology (AU), Wright-Patterson AFB OH, Dec 1992.
8. Cybenko, G. "Approximation of Superpositions of a Sigmoidal Function", *Mathematics of Control, Signals and Systems*, 2:303-314 (March 1989)

Figure 1: Electronically Trainable Analog Neural Net Architecture

Figure 2: Composite Normalized Waveforms for Three Emitters

Iterations (x1000)	Network Size (in-hid-out)	Simulator Train/Test	ETANN Test Only
200	16-16-30	82%/81%	76%
200	16-20-30	86%/85%	81%
200	16-25-30	92%/90%	77%
200	16-30-30	91%/91%	72%
200	16-35-30	92%/92%	83%

Table 1: Simulation vs ETANN Results for Various Network Sizes

Number of Epochs	Network Size	Simulator Train/ Test	ETANN Test Only
44	16-35-30	95%/93%	75%
89	16-35-30	96%/94%	83%
133	16-35-30	96%/95%	81%
177	16-35-30	96%/95%	82%

Table 2: Simulation vs ETANN Results for "Optimal" Network Size

Chip #	Classification Performance	Average Accuracy
1	572/750	76.27%
2	644/750	85.87%
3	601/750	80.13%
4	622/750	82.93%
5	607/750	80.93%
Avg	609/750	81.22%
Std	28.46/750	3.78%

Table 3: ETANN Results for Five Different Chips, Same Weight Set